

Research

The Impact of Training and Development on Employees' Performance and Productivity

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Abstract: Training is the acquisition of knowledge, skills, and competencies because of the teaching of vocational or practical skills and knowledge that relate to specific useful competencies. Organizational skills development is the output of training programs. Employees are the main assets of any organization. Every organization needs well-trained employees for performing the activities effectively and efficiently. Training and development is the continuous process of the organizations that helps to develop the skills, knowledge, and capabilities of every employee. The success of organizations depends on employee performance. At the age of globalization, training is crucial for the competent and challenging business. It is the point that needs to help to enhance the quality of work-life of employees and develop the organization. Training and development are the vital factors of enlightening the employee's performance in every organization. The purpose of the study is to find out the impact of training and development on employee performance and productivity. The study found out that employees are aware of training; employees are motivated through practice and training and development results in higher achievement and productivity. The study suggested that the training and development of all staff should be dynamically followed and made obligatory. The employer should give compulsory training programs for all employees to improve performance. The study decided that there is a need for continuous training and development, taking into deliberation the opposition, market dynamics, customer satisfaction, and net promoter score, among others.

Keywords: Training, Development, Job Satisfaction, Employee, Performance

1. Introduction

We are living in a global village. The world is becoming smaller day by day, and our business is growing larger by the impact of globalization. In this regard, companies must be competitive to face the challenges of globalization. The competitive advantages of the firm depend on the

knowledge and skills possessed by the employees (Drucker, 1999). Training and development have become one of the essential functions in most organizations because they lead to high performance in the same field as well as a critical part of the human resource department; it has a significant effect on the success of an organization through improving employee performance (Mozael, 2015). There is a significant positive relationship exists between employee training and development and employee performance (Naveed, 2014).

Nowadays, organizations are facing high competition, continuously changing technological and business environments. Globalization and ever-changing customer needs have added up more challenges in business organizations. To meet these challenges, the industries are seeking to reach their targeted profit level by ensuring proper training and development of employees. Employees are the most precious asset for any company as they can build up or destroy the reputation of the company, and they can affect profitability (Elnaga and Imran, 2013). Training is more present-day oriented that focuses on individuals' current jobs, specific skills, and abilities to perform their duties immediately. At the same time, development enhances behaviors, attitudes, and improves employee performance in an organization. It is the process of increasing the knowledge and skills of an employee, for doing a particular job. Training is of much significance in achieving the objectives of the organization by keeping in view the interest of employees and organization (Stone, 2002). Development is a long term education process utilizing a systematic and organized procedure by which managerial personnel learn conceptual and theoretical knowledge for general purpose. Training and development proves to be a parameter for enhancing the ability of the workforce for achieving the organizational objectives. The practice is seen as a useful means of coping with changes fostered by technological innovation, market competition, corporate structuring and, most importantly, it plays a crucial role in enhancing employee performance. Thus, the objective of this study is to show the impact of training and development on employees' performance.

The running organizations should deal with training necessitates worked up with altering and growing internationalization of industry, various national points of view, and a varied workforce (Abdus, 2011). Training is of much significance in achieving the objectives of the organization by keeping in view the interest of employees and the organization (Stone, 2002). Training includes but not limited to software training, management training, whereas development focuses

primarily on the activities that improve employee skills for future endeavors. Firms are now facing new changes due to the rapid pace of technological and global development. Technological advancements have brought about the need for competencies and capabilities needed to perform a specific task. To manage all corporations, need these challenges, more enhanced, and efficient training programs.

2. Literature Review

Training and development are essential for all organizations to achieve their objectives. Many types of research have done in this area for understanding the importance of training and development. According to Abbas Q. and Yaqoob (2009), this fact is of no question that the most domineering apprehension for organizations is performance. The study found that training and development had positively correlated and claimed a statistically significant relationship with employee performance and productive output.

There have been many studies conducted on this subject. HRM activities considered as a gift in the eyes of employees and training is one of them (Mahbuba, 2013). According to Iftikhar and Sirajud (2009), training and development is an important activity to increase the performance of the employees. Without the training, the organization cannot achieve the organization 's strategic goals, mission, and effectiveness. On the other hand, Miller and Osinski (2002); Rajasekar and Khan (2013) focused and analyzed that employee training & development is one of the essential parts of human resources management with the identification of organizational need, technique, and procedure at different industrial perspectives.

Employee Training

Training is the learning process that is an indispensable part of human resource development. According to Abbas Z. (2014), training as an essential element to an employee for the development of the companies because some of the employees have lack knowledge skills and competencies and failed to accomplish the task on a timely basis. Besides, training is a learning activity directed towards the acquisition of specific knowledge and skills for an occupation or task. The focus of practice is the job or task, for example, the need to have efficiency and safety in the operation of particular machines or equipment, or the need for an active sales force to mention but a few (Cole, 2002).

According to Saleem et al. (2011), training is an organized increase from the know-how skills and sensations needed for staff members to execute efficiently in the offered process, as well as to operate in the underlying situation. Furthermore, training also increases the abilities of the employee's very effective way by motivating them and converting them in to organize well and well-mannered, which ultimately affects the performance of the organization.

However, Laing (2009) training is defined as an indicator to enhance superior skills, knowledge, capabilities, and outlook of the employees that result in the adequate performance of the workers. Moreover, he adds one more thing, that is, training extends the production of the organization. In line with this is they believe that exercise is an important means to improve the employees' productivity, which ultimately affects the organization's performance and effectiveness (Singh and Mohanty, 2012).

According to Nunvi (2006), training programs directed towards maintaining and improving current job performance while development seeks to enhance skills for future jobs. Besides, Armstrong (1996) emphasized that training should be developed and practiced within the organization by appreciating the learning of theories and approaches if training is to be well understood. Exercise is a type of activity that is planned, systematic, and it results in an enhanced level of skill, knowledge, and competency that is necessary to perform work effectively Gordon (, 1992). On the other hand, development is a broad ongoing multi-faceted set of activities (training activities among them) aimed at bringing someone or an organization up to another threshold of performance, often to perform some job or a new role in the future (McNamara, 2008).

While Singh and Mohanty (2012) explained in their research that training is an essential tool to enhance the workforce performance and it "ll ultimately increase the worth of an organization, but organization ought to be balanced amongst training worth and training disbursement. Besides, Chris (2011), employee training is essential for the organization to develop the performance of the employees, and the organization should evaluate the training program as per the objectives and missions.

In the same way, training enhancement of skills about a particular job while development has its scope stretched across the growth and personal development of the employees Obisi (2011).

Moreover, Cambell (1971) has given his views as training improves the skill level of technical staff during a short period for a specific objective while development allows the managers to learn and grow during a long term learning period having a wide-ranging goal. Also, Armstrong M. (2009) has differentiated training from development by putting his concept into words that event is meant to acquire new knowledge and skills that help to progress into some future job requirements while exercise helps in gaining those competencies that enable the employees to better perform in their present jobs.

Further researchers added that technological developments, atomization, mechanization, changing environment, and organizational change have gradually led some employers to the realization that success relies on the skills and abilities of their employees, and this means considerable and continuous investment in training and development Khan et al. (2011). They were training the act of increasing the knowledge, skills, abilities of an employee for doing a specific job. It is an organized increase from the know-how skills and sensations needed for staff members to execute efficiently in the offered process, as well as to operate in the underlying situation Saleem et al. (2011). Moreover, Laing (2009) assumed that training as an indicator to enhance superior skills, knowledge, capabilities, and outlook of the employees that result in the adequate performance of the workers.

However, Singh and Mohanty (2012) believe that training is an important means to improve the employee's productivity, which ultimately affects the organization's performance and effectiveness. On the other hand, training must be talked in such a way that it covers the employee's performance-development needs and is following their job descriptions. In addition to the previous arguments, McConnell (2004) supports a partnership approach between the employees and their companies in determining training needs, as well as the involvement of the employees in setting up training goals. Besides, Mehrdad et al. (2009) also said that training techniques are classified into behavioral or On-the-job (orientations, job instruction training, apprenticeships, internships and assistantships, job rotation, and coaching) and cognitive or off-the-job (Lectures, computer-based training, games, and simulations, etc.

Mahbuba (2013) assumed that trainer 's role is shifting from a simple task of providing skills to an active communicator who makes an effort in achieving training as well as organizational objectives. The main aim of the exercise is to improve the knowledge and skills, change the

attitude and behavior of the employees so that they can quickly adapt the new technology in the organization for production. As a result, the turnover and absenteeism rate will be less. Well-trained employees show both quantity and quality performance. There is less wastage of time, money, and resources if employees are appropriately trained, James et al. (2014).

Employee Development

Employees are always regarded with development in career-enhancing skills, which leads to employee motivation and retention for the success of the organizations as well as for their carrier. There is no doubt that a well-trained and developed staff will be a valuable asset to the company and thereby will increase the chances of their efficiency and effectiveness in discharging their duties. On the other hand, development means those learning opportunities designed to help employees to grow. Progress is not primarily skills-oriented. Instead, it provides general knowledge and attitudes, which will be helpful to employers in higher positions. Development programs are regarded as a specific framework for helping employees to develop their personal and professional skills, knowledge, attitudes, behavior, and consequently improve their abilities to perform a specific task in the organization. It provides knowledge about the business environment, management principles and techniques, human relations, accurate industry analysis, and the like is useful for better management of the company. According to Nalder (1984), to achieve present and future goals, human resource managers must focus on human resource development behavior, so for enhancing employee's performance by equipping them with new abilities and skills to perform their job.

The Effect of Training and Development on Performance and Productivity

Employee training plays an essential role in developing performance and productivity for achieving high-level output, thereby leading to increased company strength in the competitive marketplace (Nassazi, 2013). There are many differences between organizational performance and employee performance. Purcell, Kinnie, and Hutchinson (2003) and Harrison (2000) perceived performance and productivity in terms of employee performance. However, Guest (1997) and Swart et al. (2005) viewed performance as an organizational performance as a whole. There is a massive relationship between employee performance and organizational performance when increased employee performance leads to increased general organizational performance. Therefore, employee performance is a function of organizational performance. Training

programs play a significant role in increasing levels of employee competencies. Therefore, there are levels of skills, knowledge, and abilities for employees to enhance in the future, which would lead to the attainment of effective organizational performance. (Wright & Geroy, 2001). Training is an attempt to provide benefits to help employees to enhance their abilities, knowledge, behavior, and competencies in the workplace to achieve organizational goals. (Appiah, 2010; Harrison, 2000; Guest, 1997). Wright and Geroy (2001) claimed that effective training programs are essential to increase employee competencies; it also contributes to enhancing knowledge, skills and necessary information for future jobs thereby achieving desirable organizational performance. Pigors and Myers (1989) stated that effective training contributed to increased employee satisfaction and reduced absenteeism and turnover thereby increasing the feeling of comfort amongst employees leading to a sense of achievement for employees to develop their inherent abilities. Early planned training by trainers for trainees will help achieve desired benefits easily. Therefore, Kenney and Reid (1986) stated that the training aims to improve job performance and planned training contribute to enhancing effective performance for employees.

3. Objectives of the Study

The study investigated the impact of training and development on employee performance. This research work looks at training and development as an HRM practice and its effect on employee performance and productivity in the organization. Surely, the study aims to find out:

- The factors affecting the training and development of employee performance
- The impact of training and development on organizational productivity
- The impact of training on employee satisfaction
- The need for employee training in an organization

4. Methodology of the Study

Sample and Data Collection

The present study is based on primary data and data were collected through structured questionnaires among the different employees in the organization in Bangladesh. A convenience sampling technique was used for this study and sample size of the study is 50. The response rate was agreeable. The data was gathered by using a self-administered questionnaire, and the participation was voluntary. The collected data were analyzed by using SPSS-20.

Measures and Scales

Two variables were used in this study, i.e., training and development, employee performance, and job satisfaction. Equally, ten questions of training and development and employee performance were used. Job satisfaction had two issues that were adopted from the study of (Cook and Heptworth, 1981). All variables were measured using a 2-point liker scale in which two represented yes to no.

5. Analysis and Results

The primary purpose of this study is to evaluate the impact of training and development on employee performance in the organization. Here data have been gathered on the sampled respondents of the effects of training and development on employees' performance, motivation, job satisfaction of the organization. The findings of this research study and the subsequent evaluation carried out on the responses reflect the critical areas of training and development and its challenges on employee performance, motivation, retention, and morale. Findings from Employees a total number of thirty (50) employees were selected to provide answers to the structured questionnaire. Analysis of survey data is given bellow-

Figure 1: Do you think your organization's produced pieces of training are enough for you to achieve your performance?

Source: Questionnaire Survey

From the above graph, it is said that 65 percent of employees agree with this training content. Thirty-five percent have disagreed with this statement. Though the majority is supporting the content, here, the organization should change the training content in such ways where all the employees feel the interest to attend the training for better performance.

Figure 2: Do you think the training and development program has a positive impact on developing an organization?

Source: Questionnaire Survey

This chart is telling that 60 percent of employees are agreed with this statement. Forty percent have disagreed with this content.

Figure 3: Do you think the training improves your skills, knowledge, and attitude

Source: Questionnaire Survey

From this chart, it is clear that among 50 respondents, 40 respondents are agreed with the statement, while ten respondents are not agreed with the account. So it can be said that training has a high influential impact on employee performance.

Figure 4: Does the training lead you to be satisfied with your job?

Source: Questionnaire Survey

From the above graph, it is said that 70 percent of employees agree with this training content. Thirty percent have disagreed with this statement. So from this, it is stated that the majority of the employees are decided that training is helpful for their job.

Figure 5: Training enhance productivity and performance

Source: Questionnaire Survey

From the above figure, it is found that from the total 50 respondents, all of them are agreed with the statement that training always enhances their productivity and performance.

Table 1. The training program is compulsory for the employees for better performance and productivity

Responses	Frequency	Percentage
YES	35	70
NO	15	30
CAN "T SAY	-	-
Total	50	%

Source: Questionnaire Survey

From the analysis, 70 % of the employees beliefs that a training program is compulsory for better performance, and 30 % of employees do not agree with this statement.

Table 2. Frequency of Training and Development has a positive impact on performance.

Responses	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	35	70
No	10	20
Can't Say	5	15
Total	50	100 %

Source: Questionnaire Survey

From table two it shows that among 50 employees 70% believed training has a positive impact on organization while 20% employees are not thought with this statement and also 15% employees are cannot say anything about this statement.

Table 3. What type of training have you received from your organization that directly effects performance?

Responses	Frequency	Percentage
On- The Job	40	80
Off- The Job Training	10	20
External Training	-	-
Refresher	-	-
Mentoring	-	-
Total	50	100 %

Source: Questionnaire Survey

The table is telling that 80% of employees are expressed that on-the-job training directly affects performance. On the other hand, 20% of employees are believed that off-the-job exercise directly affects performance. So we can say that the practice has a positive impact on employee's performance.

Table 4. How often you receive training from your organization to improve performance and productivity.

Responses	Frequency	Percentage
Quarterly	25	50
Twice In A Year	16	32

Once In A Year	9	18
Rarely	-	-
None	-	-
Total	50	100 %

Source: Questionnaire Survey

From the above table, we can say that among 50 employees, 50 %employees believed that a quarterly training program improves the performance and 32% of employees are expressed that twice in year training improve performance. On the other hand, 18 % once in year training can improve performance and productivity. Here majority percent are believed with this statement.

Table 5. The training program helps to create job satisfaction in the quality of work life.

Responses	Frequency	Percentage
True	19	38
False	31	62
Total	50	100%

Source: Questionnaire Survey

The above table was telling that among 50 respondents, 38% of respondents believed the training program helps to create job satisfaction, and 62% of respondent's don't believe this statement. The majority percent of respondents do not agree with this content.

6. Discussion and Findings of the Study

Training is one of the most potent motivators, which can lead to many possible benefits for both individuals and the organization that helps to achieve objectives of the organization. The aim of the study is to examine the impact of training and development on employee's performance. The aim is to evaluate and analyze the effect of training and development of employee's performance. To achieve these objectives a sample of 10 respondents were selected. The study revealed some findings like average employee strongly belief that training improves skills, knowledge, and abilities and it helps to create their job satisfaction of employees. This statement is similar with the view of Ewuim and Ubochi (2007). Basically better productivity depends on proper training to the employees.

7. Conclusion and Recommendation

Training and development is an essential aspect of human resource management. The organization needs to get skilled and capable employees for better performance, and employees will be competent when they have the knowledge and skill of doing the task. Training and

development would provide opportunities for the employees to make a better career life and get a better position in the organization. HR. Department is continuously hiring skilled people from a broad market and thus provides pieces of training to cope with global challenges. Through various HR activities and training programs, they retain talents in the organization, ensure a career path for performers to perform more efficiently and effectively to contribute more and more. Many organizations have realized the importance of the role of training and development programs as it increases the organization's staff efficiency, skills, and productivity. To achieve the benefits of a training initiative. The research shows that there is a strong impact of training and development on employee performance. All Employees of the organizations find their training and development benefits for their performance. Employers should be provided with more training programs to reduce the cost of recruiting and training new staff members. On the other hand, the provision of feedback to employees after training is recommended for employees to become aware of areas where they can improve their performance.

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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